

TRANSFORMATIVE INFLUENCE OF SOIL TESTING ON FARMING OUTPUT IN YAVATMAL DISTRICT

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of soil testing on the cost of cultivation and yield performance in cotton farming in Yavatmal district, Maharashtra. Farmers were categorized into three groups based on their level of adoption of soil test recommendations: high, medium, and low adopters. Data were collected from 60 farmers through personal interviews, with a focus on input utilization, costs, and returns. The study found that high adopters, who adhered closely to recommended fertilizer doses, experienced significantly higher yields and lower production costs compared to low adopters, who often overused or underused fertilizers.

High adopters achieved an average yield of 22 quintals per hectare and a benefit-cost (B:C) ratio of 1.5, while medium adopter produce 18 quintal per hectare with B:C ratio 1.32, low adopters produced 16 quintals per hectare with a B:C ratio of 1.19. The analysis also revealed that high adopters reduced per quintal production costs by 29%, showcasing the economic benefits of following soil test recommendations. Medium adopters, yielding 18 quintals per hectare, fell between the two groups in terms of cost efficiency and profitability. Despite the clear advantages, the adoption rate remains low, with 66.66% of farmers categorized as low adopters, indicating the need for enhanced awareness and accessibility to soil testing services.

This study underscores the importance of soil testing in optimizing input use, reducing cultivation costs, and improving yields, advocating for wider adoption to boost productivity and sustainability in cotton farming.

Keywords: Cotton, Soil Test, Cost return, B:C ratio

Introduction

Soil is the foundation of agricultural production, supplying essential nutrients to crops. Maintaining soil health is crucial for sustaining high levels of productivity. Cotton, often referred to as "White Gold," is a vital crop in India, especially in regions like Yavatmal district. However, improper nutrient management due to either overuse or underuse of fertilizers can lead to declining yields and soil degradation. To address these challenges, soil testing has emerged as a valuable tool in modern agriculture. By analysing the nutrient content and deficiencies in the soil, farmers can apply fertilizers more efficiently, ensuring optimal crop growth while minimizing wastage. This practice not only enhances productivity but also contributes to sustainable farming by maintaining soil fertility over time.

The present study was undertaken to explore the transformative influence of soil testing on cotton farming in Yavatmal district. It aims to assess how farmers who adopt soil testing practices benefit in terms of yield, cost of cultivation, and overall profitability, compared to those who rely on traditional methods.

Methodology

The present study was carried out in Yavatmal district, focusing on the transformative influence of soil testing on farming output for the year

Result and Discussion**Table 1 The level of adoption of soil testing farmers as per recommendation**

Sr no	Adoption Level	Farmers	Percentage
1	High Adoption	9	15.00
2	Medium Adoption	11	18.33
3	Low Adoption	40	66.66
Total		60	100.00

Mean = 0.36 Standard deviation = 0.74 Adoption Index = 36.21%

It is observed from the table 1. The mean for the given research is 0.36 of the given data calculated by the adoption index formula. The reason behind the low mean and high standard deviation (0.74) in the given research is the data is very dispersed and the data contain also contain the negative value the negative value are come from the farmer using the excessive amount of the fertilizer that's why the negative values are in the calculation as the based on the formula.

From the given data the 9 farmers have the high adoption rate is about 15% .11 farmers have the medium adoption rate which about the

2023-24. The study exclusively targeted farmers who conducted soil testing, aiming to assess the benefits derived from the practice. A purposive sampling method was employed to select the study area, as Yavatmal is known for its significant agricultural activity and adoption of soil testing.

Two tehsils, namely Kalamb and Babhulgaon were selected based on their high agricultural output and the concentration of farmers using soil testing services. From each tehsil, specific villages were identified for data collection, including Manjarwaghal, Gandha and Pimpalkhuti in Kalamb; Kriahnapur, Paloti and Antargaon in Babhulgaon. A total of 60 farmers who regularly performed soil testing were randomly selected from these villages. The required primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire, and face-to-face interviews were conducted to gather detailed information about farming practices, soil testing benefits, and fertilizer usage.

For analysing the data, a simple tabular analysis was applied. The cost of cultivation was calculated using standard cost concepts, including Cost A, B, and C approaches, to determine both direct and indirect costs. The study also involved a comparison between low, medium, and high adopters of soil testing recommendations, with a focus on key indicators such as yield, fertilizer efficiency, and overall profitability.

18.33% and the 40 farmers have the low adoption rate means 66.66%.The maximum farmer are not using the fertilizer as the recommended by after the soil test, they using their traditional way and as per their wish.

The adoption index for the given research is 36.21%. The very low of the adoption index it can be calculated by the averaging the all-individual farmer adoption.

Table 2 Per hectare cost of cultivation of different level of adopters

Sr no.	Particulars		Low Adopters (N=40)		Medium Adopters (N=11)		High Adopters (N=9)	
			Cost	Percentage to Cost 'C ₃ '	Cost	Percentage to Cost 'C ₃ '	Cost	Percentage to Cost 'C ₃ '
1.	Hired human labour (Days)	Male	3413.25	3.25	5200	5.02	3644	3.58
		Female	28152	26.82	26878	25.97	25868	25.43
	Sub total		31565.25	30.07	32078	30.99	29512	29.01
2.	Bullock labour (Days)		7750	7.38	6750	6.52	7500	7.37
3.	Machinery (Hour)		5185.78	4.94	4139	4.00	4294	4.22
4.	Seed (Kg)		3817.5	3.64	4155.18	4.01	3725	3.66
5.	Manure (Tonnes)		3600	3.43	4000	3.86	2078	2.04
6.	Fertilizers	N	3988	3.80	2801.6	2.71	2928	2.88
		P	3312	3.16	2342.43	2.26	1800	1.77
		K	2274	2.17	2311.82	2.23	1557	1.53
	Sub total		9574	9.12	7455.85	7.20	6285	6.18
7.	Irrigation charges (Rs)		264.29	0.25	300	0.29	228	0.22
8.	Repairing Charges (Rs)		114.29	0.11	260	0.25	183.33	0.18
9.	Incidental charges (Rs)		170.7	0.16	189	0.18	192.11	0.19
10.	Plant protection (Rs)		3988.93	3.80	3500.55	3.38	4088	4.02
11.	Working capital (1 to 10) (Rs)		66030.74	62.91	62827.58	60.70	58085.44	57.10
12.	Int. on Working. Capital @ 6% / annum (Rs)		3961.84	3.77	3769.65	3.64	3485.12	3.43
13.	Depreciation cost (Rs)		6783.26	6.46	5930.92	5.73	3908	3.84
14.	Land revenue, Cess and Other taxes (Rs)		59.7	0.06	61.64	0.06	61.56	0.06
15.	Cost 'A' (11 to 14)		76835.54	73.20	72589.79	70.13	65540.12	64.42
16.	Interest on fixed capital @ 10 % per annum		1915.00	1.82	2179.07	2.11	2606.82	2.56
17.	Rental Value of Land		19150.05	18.24	21790.72	21.05	26068.24	25.62
18.	COST B (15 TO 17)		97900.59	93.27	96559.59	93.29	94215.19	92.61
19	Family human labour (Days)		4790	4.56	4520	4.37	5688.88	5.59
			2272.39	2.16	2430	2.35	1826.88	1.80
	Subtotal		7062.39	6.73	6950	6.71	7515.77	7.39
20	Cost 'C' (18 To 19)		104962.98	100.00	103509.59	100.00	101730.95	100.00
21	Gross value of Produce (Rs)		114960		130806		156470.6	
22	Per quintal cost of production (Rs)		6560.18		5750.53		4624.13	
23	B:C Ratio		1.19		1.32		1.5	

The table 2 outlines a comprehensive analysis of the cost of cultivation across three categories of adopters: low adopters (N=40), medium adopters (N=11), and high adopters (N=9). Each category is evaluated based on various expense categories, their respective costs, and the percentage contribution of these costs to the overall total (Cost C).

In the hired human labour category, low adopters spend ₹3,413.25 on male labour and ₹28,152 on female labour, resulting in a subtotal of ₹31,565.25, accounting for 30.07% of Cost C. Medium adopters incur higher costs of ₹5,200 for male labour and ₹26,878 for female labour, totalling ₹32,078, which represents 30.99% of Cost C. High adopters, however, spend less on hired male labour (₹3,644) and slightly less on female labour (₹25,868), bringing their subtotal to ₹29,512, which is 29.01% of Cost C.

Bullock labour costs indicate a slight increase in expenses as we move from low (₹7,750 or 7.38% of Cost C) to high adopters (₹7,500 or 7.37% of Cost C), with medium adopters spending ₹6,750 (6.52% of Cost C).

For machinery costs, low adopters incur ₹5,185.78 (4.94% of Cost C), while medium adopters spend ₹4,139 (4.00% of Cost C) and high adopters spend ₹4,294 (4.22% of Cost C), indicating that machinery costs are relatively stable across all adopter levels.

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When it comes to seed expenses, low adopters pay ₹3,817.50 (3.64% of Cost C), while medium adopters spend slightly more at ₹4,155.18 (4.01% of Cost C). High adopters reduce their costs to ₹3,725 (3.66% of Cost C).

Manure costs show a different trend, where low adopters spend ₹3,600 (3.43% of Cost C), medium adopters spend ₹4,000 (3.86% of Cost C), and high adopters significantly reduce their expenditure to ₹2,078 (2.04% of Cost C).

In terms of fertilizers, low adopters spend ₹9,574 on a combination of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, representing 9.12% of Cost C. Medium adopters manage to lower their fertilizer costs to ₹7,455.85 (7.20% of Cost C), while high adopters incur the lowest fertilizer costs at ₹6,285 (6.18% of Cost C).

The irrigation, repairing, and incidental charges remain relatively low across all adopters, with percentages generally hovering around 0.25% to 0.29% of Cost C for irrigation and 0.11% to 0.25% for repairing charges.

The plant protection costs vary slightly among the groups. Low adopters spend ₹3,988.93 (3.80% of Cost C), while medium adopters spend slightly less at ₹3,500.55 (3.38% of Cost C), and high adopters spend a bit more at ₹4,088 (4.02% of Cost C).

Overall, working capital costs reflect a consistent trend, with low adopters at ₹66,030.74 (62.91% of Cost C), medium adopters at ₹62,827.58 (60.70% of Cost C), and high adopters at ₹58,085.44 (57.10% of Cost C).

Interest on working capital also shows a downward trend from low adopters at ₹3,961.84 (3.77% of Cost C) to high adopters at ₹3,485.13 (3.43% of Cost C).

Depreciation costs are highest for low adopters at ₹6,783.26 (6.46% of Cost C) and gradually decrease to ₹5,930.92 (5.73% of Cost C) for medium adopters and ₹3,908 (3.84% of Cost C) for high adopters.

Land revenue, cess, and other taxes remain fairly consistent across the groups, each contributing around 0.06% of Cost C.

The total Cost A (sum of working capital, interest, depreciation, and taxes) shows a downward trend from low adopters at ₹76,835.54 (73.20% of Cost C) to high adopters at ₹65,540.13 (64.42% of Cost C).

In terms of fixed costs, the interest on fixed capital and the rental value of land highlights the varying expenses across the adopter levels. Low adopters incur interest of ₹1,915.00 (1.82% of Cost C), while medium adopters face slightly higher costs of ₹2,179.07 (2.11% of Cost C), and high adopters have costs of ₹2,606.82 (2.56% of Cost C). The rental value of land is also higher for high adopters (₹26,068.24 or 25.62% of Cost C) compared to low adopters (₹19,150.05 or 18.24% of Cost C).

Cost B shows low adopters at ₹97,900.60 (93.27% of Cost C) and high adopters at ₹94,215.19 (92.61% of Cost C).

In terms of family human labour, low adopters spend ₹4,790 (4.56% of Cost C), medium adopters spend ₹4,520 (4.37% of Cost C), and high adopters incur higher costs at ₹5,688.88 (5.59% of Cost C). The total family labour costs add up to ₹7,062.39 (6.73% of Cost C) for low adopters, ₹6,950 (6.71% of Cost C) for medium adopters, and ₹7,515.77 (7.39% of Cost C) for high adopters.

Finally, Cost C, which aggregates all the expenses, shows low adopters at ₹1,04,962.99, medium adopters at ₹1,03,509.59, and high adopters at ₹1,01,730.95, reflecting the overall financial landscape of these farming practices.

The gross value of produce for each group also highlights a positive correlation between adoption levels and profitability. Low adopters achieve a gross value of ₹1,14,960, medium adopters generate ₹1,30,806, and high adopters lead with ₹1,56,470.60.

The per quintal cost of production also demonstrates a trend where low adopters have the highest cost at ₹6,560.19, while medium adopters lower their cost to ₹5,750.53, and high adopters further reduce it to ₹4,624.13.

Lastly, the B:C ratio indicates that as the level of adoption increases, the ratio improves, with low adopters at 1.19, medium adopters at 1.32, and high adopters at 1.5, suggesting that higher adoption of recommended practices leads to better financial returns for farmers.

Table 3 Profitability and cost of cultivation of cotton producer

Sr No	Particulars	Low adopters(N=40)	Medium adopters(N=11)	High adopters(N=9)
1.	Yield(q)	16	18	22
2.	Increase in output (%)	-	12.5	37.5
3.	Gross return (Rs/ha)	114960	130806	156470.6
4.	Cost (Rs/ha)			
	a)Cost A	76835.54	72589.79	65540.12
	b)Cost B	97900.59	96559.59	94215.19
	c)Cost C	104962.98	103509.59	101730.95
5.	Profit in Rs/ha			
	a)Cost A	38124.46	58216.21	90930.48
	b)Cost B	17059.41	34246.41	62255.41
	c)Cost C	9997.02	27296.41	54739.65
6.	Unit cost assessment (per quintal cost) (Rs/ha)			
	a)Cost A	4802.22	4032.76	2979.09
	b)Cost B	6112.78	5364.42	4282.50
	c)Cost C	6560.18	5750.53	4624.13
7.	Unit cost reduction (per quintal cost) (Rs/ha)			
	a)Cost A		769.46	1823.13
	b)Cost B		748.36	1830.28
	c)Cost C		809.65	1936.05
8.	B:C ratio			
	a)Cost A	1.496	1.80	2.38
	b)Cost B	1.17	1.35	1.66
	c)Cost C	1.09	1.26	1.53

The table 3 reveal a detailed comparison of the cost of cultivation, yield, gross returns, and profitability for low, medium, and high adopters of agricultural practices.

Starting with yield, low adopters achieve a production level of 16 quintals per hectare. Medium adopters see a notable increase, yielding 18 quintals, which reflects a 12.5% improvement over their low-adopting counterparts. High adopters demonstrate the most significant productivity, achieving 22 quintals per hectare, representing a substantial 37.5% increase in yield compared to low adopters.

The increase in output percentage further emphasizes the effectiveness of adopting improved agricultural practices. Medium adopters experience a 12.5% increase, while high adopters benefit from a remarkable 37.5% boost in their output.

In terms of gross returns, there is a clear distinction between the different adoption levels. Low adopters generate a gross return of ₹1,14,960 per hectare. Medium adopters earn ₹1,30,806, indicating a positive shift in financial performance with improved practices. High adopters enjoy the highest gross return, amounting to ₹1,56,470.60, showcasing a strong correlation between the level of technology adoption and financial returns.

When examining the costs of cultivation, Cost A, which includes working capital and interest, reveals that low adopters incur costs of ₹76,835.54. Medium adopters have slightly lower costs at ₹72,589.79, while high adopters manage to keep costs down further to ₹65,540.12. As for Cost B, which accounts for fixed capital and rental values, low adopters face expenses of ₹97,900.59, while medium adopters have

costs of ₹96,559.59, and high adopters have slightly lower costs at ₹94,215.19. Finally, looking at Cost C, which includes family labour, low adopters have a total cost of ₹1,04,962.98, medium adopters at ₹1,03,509.59, and high adopters at ₹1,01,730.95.

The profitability analysis shows that low adopters achieve a profit of ₹38,124.46 per hectare based on Cost A, while medium adopters make ₹58,216.21, and high adopters realize a profit of ₹90,930.48. This trend continues with Cost B, where low adopters earn ₹17,059.41 in profit, medium adopters have ₹34,246.41, and high adopters reach ₹62,255.41. Under Cost C, low adopters' profit stands at ₹9,997.02, medium adopters earn ₹27,296.41, and high adopters significantly benefit with profits of ₹54,739.65.

Additionally, the unit cost assessment reveals that the cost per quintal of production decreases as the level of adoption increases. For Cost A, low adopters incur a cost of ₹4,802.22 per quintal, medium adopters have a lower cost of ₹4,032.76, and high adopters achieve a more favourable cost of ₹2,979.09. The same trend is seen in Cost B and Cost C, indicating that higher adoption levels correlate with reduced production costs.

The unit cost reduction shows similar patterns, where the reduction per quintal cost is higher for medium and high adopters compared to low adopters.

Finally, the benefit-cost ratio (B:C ratio) highlights the financial viability of different adoption levels. For Cost A, low adopters have a B:C ratio of 1.496, medium adopters have a ratio of 1.80, and high adopters achieve a robust ratio of 2.38. In Cost B, the ratios are 1.17 for low adopters, 1.35 for medium adopters, and 1.66 for high adopters, while under Cost C, low adopters have a ratio of 1.09, medium adopters a ratio of 1.26, and high adopters a ratio of 1.53. This analysis indicates that higher levels of adoption not only increase yield and gross returns but also improve overall profitability and financial sustainability for farmers.

Conclusion

The study reveals that adopting soil testing recommendations significantly improves the cost efficiency, yield, and profitability of cotton farmers in Yavatmal district. High adopters, who followed soil test recommendations, achieved the highest average yield of 22 quintals per hectare, with a per quintal production cost of ₹4,624.13 and a B:C ratio of 1.5. In contrast, low adopters produced 16 quintals per hectare with a higher production cost of ₹6,560.18 and a lower B:C ratio of 1.19. Medium adopters performed better than low adopters but still lagged behind high adopters, yielding 18 quintals with a B:C ratio of 1.32.

Overall, high adopters reaped greater financial benefits, with a profit of ₹54,739.65 per hectare compared to ₹9,997.02 for low adopters.

Despite these advantages, the adoption index of 36.21% reflects a low rate of adherence to soil test recommendations, with 66.66% of farmers classified as low adopters. This calls for greater efforts to raise awareness and improve access to soil testing services, as adopting these practices can optimize input use, reduce costs, and significantly boost farmers' profitability and sustainability.

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